

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Screening rice for tolerance for salt stress and submergence

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Low-lying areas along the creeks of Andamans are regularly submerged with tidal seawater, particularly during the wet season. Suitable rice varieties are needed for successful cultivation.

We screened 30 salt-tolerant rice varieties and salt-tolerant checks Pokkali and Nona Bokra using close spacing under simulated conditions in fiberglass tanks.

The tanks were filled with soil supplemented at the rate of 60 kg N/ha

(half as basal and half as topdressing) as urea and 30 kg of K as muriate of potash. Soil electrical conductance was adjusted to 6.0 ± 1 dS/m and soil pH to 5.0. Plants were submerged up to the leaf tips for 1 wk at both the active vegetative phase and panicle initiation stage with saline water ($EC = 5$ dS/m $\pm$ 0.5).

Sixteen of the genotypes survived to yield grain (see table). Although tolerant check Pokkali gave more yield, the other tolerant check Nona Bokra died at the vegetative phase. All varieties were less than 1 m tall except IR51485-2B-20-2B and RD15. RD15 had the most panicle-bearing tillers/plant (3.1). IET10682, closely followed by IR47449-3B-9-2B, had the greatest

panicle length. Percent grain sterility was highest in IR9884-54-3-IE-P1.

IET10682, CR1009, IR51337-2B-3-2B IR4819-77-3-2, IR47441-3B-1-2B, B2443B-KN-10-1-1-1, IR37003-15-3-3-3, IR51485-2B-20-2B and Pokkali showed good phenotypic indices at the vegetative phase as indicated by scores of 1-3 (see table). But only IR51485-2B-20-2B, IR47441-3B-1-2B, BR2443B-KN-10-1-1-1, and Pokkali had the same high scores at maturity. The tolerant check Pokkali outperformed the others at both the vegetative and ripening phases. No phenotypic characteristic was consistently correlated with salt tolerance (see table).

Varities IR51485-2B-20-2B and IR47441-3B-1-2B are promising for areas where salinity is a problem at both the seedling and maturity stages. ■

Performance of some salt-tolerant rice varieties under 1 wk of submergence in saline water ($EC = 5$ dS/m).

Variety	Source	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grain sterility (%)	Seed yield/plant (g)	Salt tolerance ^a	
							Vegetative phase	Ripening phase
IR51485-2B-20-2B	IRRI, Philippines	132.3	2.0	23.6	7.0	7.4	3	1
IR47441-3B-20-2B	IRRI, Philippines	80.0	3.0	20.0	25.1	6.0	2	2
Pokkali (check)	India	76.0	2.1	20.3	10.7	5.6	1	2
B2443B-KN-10-1-1-1	Indonesia	83.2	2.2	19.0	5.9	5.3	3	2
IET11353 (IR16294-C59-1-30)	IRRI, Philippines	87.7	2.0	20.3	33.8	4.1	4	4
IR47449-3B-9-2B	IRRI, Philippines	90.5	2.2	24.0	23.1	3.7	9	5
IET10682	Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad, India	99.7	1.1	24.3	34.7	3.7	1	5
RD15	CSSRI Sub-Station Canning, West Bengal, India	112.0	3.1	18.5	8.1	3.5	3	5
Cablak	IRRI, Philippines	77.2	2.5	19.5	39.2	3.3	8	5
C22	Philippines	77.5	2.4	18.0	3.3	3.3	9	5
X73-3-9	Myanmar	80.6	1.8	18.6	11.4	2.7	4	6
IR37003-15-3-3-3	IRRI, Philippines	79.2	1.8	20.0	35.4	2.2	3	7
IET11355 (C200-BD25-16)	DRR, Hyderabad, India	97.0	1.6	15.0	13.0	2.2	4	8
IR51337-2B-3-2B	IRRI, Philippines	76.3	1.3	15.0	8.1	1.6	2	8
IR52471-2B-2-2B	IRRI, Philippines	67.0	1.0	18.2	27.0	1.5	4	7
IR9884-54-3-IEP1	IRRI, Philippines	80.0	2.0	20.2	43.9	1.2	7	7
IR4819-77-3-2	IRRI, Philippines	91.5	2.3	20.0	4.6	1.0	2	9
CR1009	India	84.0	2.2	19.0	9.8	0.7	1	9
Range		67.0-132.3	1.0-3.1	15.0-24.3	3.3-43.9	0.7-7.4		
Mean		87.31	2.033	19.63	19.11	3.27		
SE		3.6221	0.1323	0.5968	3.2006	0.4418		

^aStandard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale